

Photon, Poynting Vector and Constant Velocity Electron Part III

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In simple Newton equation cases, one deals with nonrelativistic kinetic energy and potential energy. Thus, a particle is usually moving and has momentum and kinetic energy. These may be viewed in different frames travelling with various velocities which leads to the case of special relativity (no potential) of $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$, where m_0 is rest mass. Momentum and energy then constitute a 4-vector. In the Newtonian case, a potential is viewed as being associated with a force which changes a particle's kinetic energy.

It is possible that a potential may be part of a particle. For example, a charged particle at rest delivers an electric force and when moving both electric and magnetic forces ($F_{\text{magnetic}} = qv \times B$) to a charged particle. Thus, a charged particle may have overall energy and momentum which represent a 4-vector, but it also has E and B fields which are involved in rendering force. These E and B fields are dependent on charge and current density (used to create the 4-vectors A and phi.) Maxwell's equations describe how E and B fields depend on sources. They also allow a photon solution (for no sources and E and B and essentially the same strength for $c=1$). This solution is equivalent to $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ with $m_0=0$.

From Maxwell's equations, one may form: d/dt EM energy density + grad . Poynting vector = $E \cdot j$ where j is current. In regions where there is no current one has 0 on the RHS. Thus, it appears that not only are there electric and magnetic forces, but there is energy and momentum associated with the EM field for a moving charge. At first, one may think this energy and momentum are isolated from the rest of the charge system which contains other mass and potentials, but this does not seem to be the case. For a charge at rest, electric energy $\frac{1}{2}EE/(8\pi^2)$ may be calculated by bringing charge, one shell at a time, to build up a spherically charged object. There is electrostatic repulsion as a shell is brought in, so work is performed which does not result in kinetic energy, but rather in electric field energy. It seems that there must be tension in the system to hold the various shells together as they would normally fly apart due to electric repulsion. Thus, the two "systems" are coupled and it does not seem to make sense to talk of EM energy and momentum as a four vector. In particular, EM energy and momentum do not transform as a 4-vector, but in a way dictated by the source and Maxwell's equations. Furthermore, if one imposes $E = m_0 + .5mv^2$ and $p = mv$ for the overall non-relativistic case, this seems to indicate that the non-EM momentum and energy also changes with v in an unusual manner.

In this note, we try to investigate some of these issues.

Newton's Equations

Newton's equations in their simplest form deal with motion. Usually one has kinetic energy plus potential energy equaling a constant. Motion, however, may be "created" by viewing an object from a frame moving at a particular velocity. This is related to special relativity which leads to $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ where m_0 is the rest mass, $E = m_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2}$ and

$p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv}$. In the low v limit, $p = mv$ and $E = m_0 + .5mvv$. Thus, for overall motion one may consider an entire system from one frame or another moving at a certain constant velocity. This type of motion is associated with a four vector.

Consider two particles at rest with masses $m_0/2$. From a frame moving with v , one may see two particles each satisfying the equation:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad \text{where } p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv} \text{ and } E = .5m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv}$$

The two particles are completely independent. One may also write one equation:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad \text{where } p = mv \text{ and } E = m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv}$$

This may lead people to think that electromagnetic energy and momentum may be treated as an independent four vector, but sources and electromagnetic energy are linked. First, they are linked through Maxwell's equations as the source appears explicitly. Secondly, when calculating electrostatic energy $.5EE/(8*3.14)$ for a point charge at rest (or spherical), work is done bringing in shells of charge. This energy appears as electrostatic energy in the field, but there is tension in the system holding the shells together. Thus, there is coupling between the electrostatic energy and a kind of binding energy of the rest of the system. If the electric field changes through motion, this binding should also change. It does not seem that electromagnetic energy and momentum can be treated as a four vector because they are coupled to the energy and momentum of the rest of the charged system. In fact, explicit calculations, say for a spherical charge, show that they are not. Only in the case of a photon does this coupling disappear, leading to a dispersion relation of $E = p$.

This begs the question: If energy and momentum create a four vector and one may calculate these for the electromagnetic fields, why are they not a 4-vector? We argue that it is because they are not independent of the momentum and energy of the rest of the system. E and B transform with v according to Maxwell's equations. These are then used to calculate energy density $.5(e_0EE + 1/\mu_0 BB)$ and the Poynting vector $1/\mu_0 E \times B$ which do not follow from a Lorentz boost of $.5e_0EE$ ($.5EE/(8*3.14)$) with 0 momentum. A Lorentz boost only applies to the whole system, electromagnetic energy/momentum as well as other energy and momentum. Components of the system, i.e. electromagnetic energy and other energy, may follow a different transformation law with changing velocity v , namely one dictated by Maxwell's equations. One may note that E and B are not four vectors either, only A and ϕ .

Electric and Magnetic Energies

For a moving spherical charge, electromagnetic energies are calculated in (1) and are:

$$\text{Electric energy} = U_0 / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad (1-vv/3)$$

$$\text{Magnetic energy} = \frac{2}{3} U_0 / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad vv$$

$$\text{EM Momentum} = \text{Integrated Poynting vector } dv = \frac{4}{3} U_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv}$$

$$(\text{= Integral } dv \text{ ExB} / (4 \cdot 3.14))$$

It may be noted that $B = (0, -vE_z, vE_y)$ and $P = (v(E_y E_y + E_z E_z), -E_x E_y v, -E_x E_y v)$. The above integral may be performed quickly in the nonrelativistic limit for which $1/\sqrt{1-vv}$ becomes 1. There is momentum flux in the y and z directions, but these integrate to 0. Nevertheless, it seems as if there is swirling motion.

$$\text{Here } U_0 = \frac{e^2}{2r} = \text{Integral } .5EE \text{ dvolume} / (4 \cdot 3.14)$$

It is pointed out in (1), that $.5v$ times EM momentum equals magnetic energy which is the nonrelativistic $.5vp = .5mvv$ result. The expressions above, however, are relativistic, and so the idea should carry over into the relativistic region, but not seem to do so.

For Lorentz boosts, rest energy should change according to $m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$. If one considers EM energy alone, the "rest" EM energy is $U_0 = \text{Integral } .5EE/(8 \cdot 3.14) \text{ d volume}$, but the energy in the moving frame is not $U_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$, but rather $E_{\text{magnetic}} + E_{\text{electric}} = U_0/\sqrt{1-vv} (1+vv/3)$. Furthermore, $E_n(\text{EM})$ and $p(\text{EM})$ in the low v limit are not linked in the usual Newtonian manner $p=mv$ and $E_n=m_0 + .5mvv$. Thus, it seems there is no reason that the non-EM mass should follow the Newtonian approach either, only the total energy and momentum.

Nevertheless, it is interesting to consider the nonrelativistic limit. In that case, $p=mv$ and $E_n = m_0 + .5mvv$. The EM energies and momentum become in such a limit:

$$\text{Electric energy} = U_0 + U_0 vv/6$$

$$\text{Magnetic energy} = \frac{2}{3} U_0 vv \quad \text{and Momentum} = \frac{4}{3} U_0 v/\sqrt{1-vv} \text{ (in the direction of } v \text{.)}$$

This seems to suggest that the non-EM energy must also change as v i.e.

$$m_1(v) = m_1(v=0) - U_0 vv/6 - \frac{2}{3} U_0 vv = m_1(v=0) - U_0 vv \quad ((1))$$

For the momentum in the low v limit

$$p(\text{nonEM } v) + p(\text{EM}) = mv = [m_1(v=0) + U_0]v \text{ so}$$

$$p(\text{nonEM } v) = m_1(v=0) + U_0)v - \frac{4}{3} U_0 v. \quad ((2))$$

It is curious that for both ((1)) and ((2)), one may have a value of $m_1(v=0)$ so small that $m_1(v)$ and $p(\text{nonEM } v)$ are both negative. This seems strange and unphysical.

Maxwell's equations do not seem to place restrictions on the mass of the charged particle, yet this particle should have tension related to holding the "charged shells" together. For the case of an electron, this problem does not arise because $m_1(v=0)$ is very much larger than the electrostatic energy which is no more than a percent or two.

It is interesting how internal components of energy and momentum may behave in completely different ways from Lorentz boost behaviour and yet the combined result must behave as a Lorentz boost.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that em energy and momentum in a charged spherical particle is linked to the rest of the energy and so each set do not form a 4-vector (p, E). There is only one four vector for the entire charged particle system. The E and B fields serve to render force to a charged particle. In creating the E and B fields, work is done which is present in the field as energy. (In the electrostatic case, one may imagine a shell of charge being added to a core sphere of charge. Work is done and there must be binding to hold the charged shells together. There are energy and momentum density values which follow from Maxwell's equation, but they do not transform according to a Lorentz boost. Instead, they behave in an unusual manner even though in (1) it is noted that for the nonrelativistic case, magnetic energy and Poynting momentum are linked in the usual Newtonian way i.e. Magnetic energy = $v/2$ Poynting momentum which does not explain why electric energy is not included as its deformation term goes as vv . Furthermore, there is no relativistic link.

If one wishes to impose $E = m_0 + .5mv^2$ and $p = mv$ overall, then the non-EM part of mass and momentum also behave in a strange manner. Furthermore, it seems that imposing overall Newtonian behaviour allows for $m(\text{nonEM } v > 0)$ and $p(\text{nonEM } v > 0)$ to both be negative which is unusual and possibly even unphysical. Even though the EM and non-EM portions should be linked by some kind of tension, Maxwell's equations link them only through charge and current.

References

1. Singal, A. Energy-momentum of the self-fields of a moving charge in classical electromagnetism (Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and General 1999)

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